
THE ECONOMY OF GERMANY AFTER THE PANDEMIC: RISKS AND PROBLEMS.

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Abstract.

The presented article is devoted to the analysis of the German economy after the pandemic. Economic processes, lockdowns during the coronavirus period are highlighted.

Situations in the financial sector, in the field of unemployment and in imports and exports are provided. It is noted that it was the period in a difficult situation that small and medium-sized businesses in the German economy suffered more losses. And also analyzed the impact of the pandemic on the German economic sector.

Keywords.

Economy, Pandemic, Import, Inflation, Unemployment

The unexpected lockdown brought countless losses to the German economy in 2020 and 2021. From the point of view of well-known analysts, a huge share of the current loss comes to the share of the service sector. Despite predictions that German GDP has the potential to reach pandemic levels again by the end of 2022, economic productivity will remain a marked "slowdown", which would not have happened if it were not for the difficult situation with new COVID-19 mutations. Germany, the economic and political leader of the European continent, like other states, has experienced a major economic crisis during the COVID-19 pandemic. The coronavirus and measures to contain it have become accustomed to the fact that the economic sector of the state fell into a deep economic crisis, but it should be noted that the pandemic did not have such negative consequences as other European economies.

At the moment, 2 main factors can be emphasized, how the pandemic directly affected the economy. First, the growth of the contingent of charged and dead led to a decrease in the supply of workers. Secondly, the measures taken by other countries to fight against the coronavirus. More precisely, if there is a restriction in the field of hospitality, tourism can adversely affect commodity production. For example, if there are no security measures, then entrepreneurs will have to close their shops temporarily or have to change production processes.

China, France, USA, UK, Japan, Italy and Germany account for 60% of the world's GDP, with 60% of manufactured goods and 41% of export goods. The German economy is also affected by these developments because the Germans have an open economy that is heavily involved in global value chains.

The pandemic has greatly affected the export of this state. The prohibition abroad, the closure of its borders to foreigners, as well as the serious business environment is the main reason for holding the recessionary period in the economic sector. At the same time, it should be emphasized that the consequences of the pandemic will have negative effects on the financial sector for a long time, since the deficit in Germany in 2021 was 153.86 billion euros. It should be noted that such a deep deficit in the German economy was in 1990.

The economic role of the middle class is quite high. 56% of GDP and 60% of jobs fall to the share of the middle class, the percentage of which is 99% of all enterprises in the country. Despite the serious test, the medium and small businesses in Germany managed to survive. It should be emphasized that the Anti-Crisis Program adopted to combat COVID-19, which indicated assistance to micro-enterprises, self-employed and individual entrepreneurs. If during the 2008 World Financial Crisis, large banks had to be rescued, then after the pandemic, medium and small businesses were in particular danger, because due to the strict quarantine measures taken in Germany, numerous enterprises such as hairdressing salons, concert agencies, business offices, grocery stores and various enterprise and service industry corporations temporarily stopped their activities. The rise in prices in Germany, as of December this year, was 5.3% compared to 2021, this is the highest figure in the last 30 years.

The Germans expect that in 2022 the headline inflation rate will not exceed 3.5%. The rate of inflation accelerated even towards the end of 2021, while prices for service products rose by a total of 5.3%. Most economic agencies believe that the peak of the crisis is over. And experts are discussing that the increase in prices for important energy resources is the main reason for the sharp increase in inflation, that is, during the reduction in the production of the planet, following the huge collapse caused by the epidemic: their tariffs jumped an average of 10.4%, in contrast to last year when tariffs fell by approximately 4.8% in 2020.

Unemployment is one of the most important economic indicators in Germany. Measures to weaken the development of COVID-19, caused by the state, had a negative impact on the activities of the population: working hours were reduced, which led to specified lockdowns in the service sector. Although in the first quarter

of 2021 the level unemployment was 6.2%, but before that the German economy experienced the highest unemployment rate – 6.4%.

The pandemic also affected changes in the dynamics of foreign trade. At the same time, it should be emphasized that not only Germany, but also the economies of its trading partners have been hit hard by COVID-19. Relations with China entered the agenda, since it was precisely because of the cessation of supplies of raw materials that there was a decrease in imports (-19.6%) and exports (-21.2%). Nevertheless, the last quarter of 2021 began a phased recovery from the recession and there was a change in the dynamics of exports (1.3%), while imports (4.1%). This is reflected in the fact that the growth rate of the German economy has recovered and the financial sector has moved to a phased transition from the crisis level thanks to the «Anti-Crisis Program» adopted at the beginning of the pandemic. As discussed above, all sectors in Germany have suffered heavy losses during the pandemic and the GDP sector has not been excepted. Germany's GDP grew by 2.7% in 2020 compared to 2019. Despite significant damage to key sectors of the economy, the German economy managed to survive after a sharp decline last year while gross value added increased by 4.4% year on year.

The pandemic has faced a decline with all sectors of the German economy. Increasing inflation and GDP, the problems of small and medium-sized businesses are the main problems of Germany after the Coronavirus, but this temporary recession is not expected to stand and dominate the economic sector of the country for a long time, although there is still a lot of work to be done related to solving the problems of the economic sector.

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